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Preparing engineering students for a lifetime of learning A case study of curricular redesign

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ABSTRACT

In response to the observation that change is the only constant in today's working environments, leading organizations in the fields of education have placed the principle of "life-long learning" (LLL) atop the curricular agenda. Also in engineering education, it is widely accepted that graduating students need to have "a recognition of the need for, and an ability to engage in life-long learning" (ABET 2013). This contribution describes a LLL trajectory that was recently developed at the Faculty of Industrial Engineering Technology, Campus Diepenbeek (KU Leuven & UHasselt). The curricular pathway and the learning environments were designed following Dochy's guidelines for "high impact learning", with student ownership and (self-)reflection as critical components. From the start, students engage in a sequence of curricular activities that integrate the acquisition of soft and hard skills in increasingly challenging problem-based project courses. The learning experiences from this curricular pathway inform the student's development of a personal LLL portfolio that not only charts but also structures and guides the student's personal learning trajectory. This LLL portfolio is initiated by a multi-angled self-assessment, which provides the basis for a self-

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constructed “PDP” (“personal development plan”). Typically, the PDP also accommodates extra-curricular activities (e.g. community service learning, MOOCs, peer teaching, ...) selected by the student to complement his or her competency profile. As with the curricular activities, the student then reflects upon these activities - now using the 4Rs model (reporting, relating, reasoning, reconstructing) – and integrates them in his or her PDP, which is, as such, continually reworked.

INTRODUCTION

It is truism to state that today’s working environments are changing at an ever increasing pace [1]. Employees, if they are to prosper within this context of perpetual change, cannot but develop a broad and flexible range of knowledge and skills. The demands on educational programs are nowadays dominated by the call for responsible and motivated individuals that show a critical attitude and ability to reflect and have efficient problem-solving skills [2]. Graduating engineers should, of course, still have strong technical knowledge and skills but increasingly, employers emphasize the importance of personal/soft skills, such as the ability to cope with stress, to be enterprising, innovative etc. [3]. Moreover, graduating engineers have to be able to work not only independently but also in teams and hence, communication skills, such as proficiency in foreign languages, writing reports, giving presentations etc. are crucial [4]. The “T-shaped engineer” of the 21st century is not just a technical specialist with in-depth knowledge of a particular domain or system, (s)he is also broadly formed and possesses boundary crossing competencies [5].

It is next to impossible to teach all of these skills comprehensively within the four or five years of the engineering curriculum. Luckily, the solution lies within the problem. Since jobs are changing, graduated engineers will have to change throughout their career. They need the attitude and ability to continually absorb new knowledge and practice new skills. In other words, they will have to engage in what is now commonly known as life-long learning (LLL). ABET, for instance, states that, by the time of their graduation, students should have acquired “a recognition of the need for, and an ability to engage in life-long learning” [6]. Currently, the importance of LLL is such that it is not just one of many competencies students should acquire, rather “it must become the guiding principle for provision and participation across the full continuum of learning contexts” [7, pp. 3-4], as stated by The Commission of the European Communities in its memorandum on LLL published in 2000.

On one hand, the ascendancy of LLL on the educational agenda provides respite to curriculum designers, as the curriculum is relieved of the burden to carry within itself the full range of specialist and generalist competencies. On the other hand, the curriculum should make sure that when they graduate, students possess a positive attitude towards life-long learning as well as the skills necessary to engage effectively in this process.

In the context of this contribution, LLL is conceived of as the process in which self-motivated individuals constantly seek for knowledge and develop skills. LLL can then be defined as a competency that implies:

- a) the willingness to look out for and take advantage of formal, non-formal and informal occasions for self-development on professional, social/civic and personal level (**attitude**);
- b) this attitude presupposes a LLL **skill set** for self-directed learning (continuous cycle):
 - a. the ability to self-assess in relation to ever-changing demands of the industrial, economic and social environment;
 - b. the ability to set goals for development;
 - c. the ability to plan and execute;
 - d. the ability to continuously (re)evaluate the LLL pathway;
 - e. the ability to draw learning gains from not only formal but also non-formal and informal learning situations;
- c) these skills presuppose **knowledge** of some fundamental concepts and techniques:
 - a. frameworks for self-assessment like the core qualities model, SWOT,...;
 - b. ways to obtain new knowledge e.g. search engines, educational centres, professional network groups (e.g. ie-net), MOOCs,....

In this contribution, we communicate on our learning trajectory towards LLL for students in Engineering Technology with a focus in Chemistry. This learning trajectory is spearheaded by a dedicated course on Lifelong Learning, but, in line with the vision of The Commission of the European Communities [7], LLL pervades the entire curricular pathway. To enable this broad approach, a didactical concept was selected that could scaffold the entire curriculum, while continuously honing students' LLL competencies. The concept chosen is the HILL-model by Dochy – or “high impact learning that lasts”, in full – the tenets of which directly prepare students for a lifetime of learning [2]. First, we explain how Dochy helps shape the LLL curricular pathway. Then, the philosophy and outline of the course on Lifelong learning are explained. Finally, some preliminary observations and remarks are discussed.

1 CURRICULAR DEVELOPMENT ACCORDING TO DOCHY

Throughout the curriculum, we aim to establish a “high impact learning” environment following the ideas of Dochy [2]. The main emphases of this high impact learning environment are summarized in *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 1. Elements for high-impact learning that lasts, according to Dochy [2]

We started from the observation that the Dochy principles firmly bolster the acquisition of LLL skills:

- LLL is prompted by the self-critical observation that there exists a **gap** between one's current and desired competencies;
- for effective LLL, **learner agency** is prerequisite as the learner himself, without institutional or top-down prompts, takes initiative to expand his professional repertoire;
- LLL is not a solitary enterprise, but it takes place in **collaborative** interaction with peers and in dialogue with a **coach** (a mentor, a teacher, an instructor, an inspirational role model, an industry leader...);
- LLL in the 21st century takes place in **hybrid learning** environments (F2F seminar settings, online learning, MOOCs,...);
- LLL implies an *action-oriented* attitude, and it is accelerated by **knowledge sharing** in networks of learners;
- LLL is not limited to **formal** learning contexts (seminars, MOOCs, trainings), but the effective LLL learner will also draw learning gains from **informal** and non-formal contexts (in leisure or community service associations, spontaneous work floor interactions, in social or non-profit organisations,...).

Now, how is the HILL-model implemented in our curriculum? One powerful way to incorporate all of these elements, is to organize group project works. For this reason, we include at least one project work each semester throughout the entire curriculum. To avoid, however, that group work becomes a “bolt-on” experience, detached from the rest of the curriculum, we have taken care to ensure that the design of the full curriculum is informed by the HILL tenets. First, the implementation of Dochy in the classic courses and lab sessions will be discussed. Then, the learning trajectory of ‘Research and engineering skills’, of which the project work is part, will be discussed.

1.1 Classic courses and lab sessions

Courses start from problems, assignments or tasks that young engineers are typically confronted with in their first job. This way students see the **urgency** to acquire the knowledge and skills that are offered to them. Through company visits or industry cases, 'real life' is brought into the class room. For instance, a chapter on heat transfer is started with the task to choose an isolation thickness for a steam conduct – revealing a knowledge gap that leads to the introduction of heat transfer laws. Each course is part of a larger learning trajectory, which is clarified in the first lesson of a course to the students. The end of such a learning trajectory is marked by an assignment in which knowledge from different courses needs to be combined, e.g. at the end of the learning trajectory 'analytical chemistry' students are given an assignment where they have to select, develop and validate an analytical method for a specific (real) problem.

Learner agency is increased by giving a certain degree of freedom to the students, both in the form of optional courses and within courses. For instance, students decide for themselves whether to attend an extra support session or to work independently on exercises.

Professors work with powerful **hybrid learning environments** in which classic methods (textbook, lectures, ...) are blended with new learning methods, e.g. group discussions, peer feedback, electronic learning platforms such as Blackboard (with online courses, evaluations, instruction movies, lab preparation modules...) and Perusall², guided self-instruction, polls on conceptual questions, etc. Students cannot simply 'sit and absorb knowledge' but they have to **actively** engage in the learning process, which does not stop when students leave the classroom. This active process also gives the professor or teaching assistant the possibility to give **continuous feedback (informal assessment)** and act as a **coach** in the learning process.

Moreover, students are encouraged to **collaborate** and **share their knowledge**. In some courses this is even part of the assessment. For instance, in the lab of Organic Chemistry, each student is responsible for one type of experiment. This means they have to instruct their fellow students, correct their calculations, observe their work and answer their questions. Only by collaborating, they can all achieve the set goals.

1.2 Learning trajectory 'Research and engineering skills'

The different elements of the HILL model are also strongly represented in the learning trajectory 'Research and engineering skills'. In the first semester, basic engineering skills such as translating a problem into equations, interpretation of graphs etc. are practiced. From the second semester onwards, each semester of the curriculum contains at least one project work (see *Fig. 2*), where students work in groups on a real-life assignment and in interaction with the problem owners (e.g. a company or a research group) (**urgency, problem based**). These (group) assignments include authentic, real life case studies that appeal to students' technological skills as well as their soft skills (communication, project management, team work). Students need to

² Perusall (www.perusall.com) is an online, collaborative application that allows students to annotate course material with questions and comments. Perusall is often used in a flipped classroom context.

display an **actionable and collaborative** attitude. They are **coached** by a supervising professor/teaching assistant, but the intensity of the given guidance decreases over the course of the curriculum. Moreover, in order to complete the assignments, students have to manage their own learning process. Students have to define the problem, decide which information to look for, outline their approach etc. In other words, they have to take their trajectory into their own hands (**learner agency**). The **assessment** of these project works combines an output-based assessment (e.g. presentation, report, journal article) with a peer-review process assessment – an approach based on Dochy's earlier work [8]. This peer assessment reviews skills such as finding information, taking initiative, listening, being critical etc. Halfway the project work, a first assessment without grades is done, the result of which is shared and discussed with the students. Through feedback from peers as well as professors and teaching-assistants, students gain insight into their skills. A second assessment at the end of the semester forms part of the grade of each individual student. The consecutive assessments also are the basis of the reflection that students do in the Lifelong Learning course, which is discussed below.

Fig. 2. Consecutive courses in the Learning trajectory 'Research and engineering skills'

2 A COURSE IN LIFELONG LEARNING

As announced above, the curriculum also includes a separate course on LLL. In the course on LLL, the aim is to show students how they can set up a learning path when there is no longer an institution (school, university) that decides for them what they should learn. This course has been running on our campus since 2013 as part of the master program (although the teaching team encourages students to start working on the course from the start of the 5th semester). Within certain boundaries (i.e. minimal

activities to be performed), students are given the freedom to determine what they want to learn, which skills they want to develop and how they will do this. They fill in a reflective form on these activities and collect these forms in a portfolio.

However, it appeared from feedback moments, the handed in portfolios, as well as individual conversations with graduated students that we were only partly reaching the premeditated goal. Even if some students really found high learning value in their activities, other students were just ‘collecting hours’. In order to improve this, and to help students set up a well-aimed learning trajectory, a new approach was initiated in 2018.

In the new approach, students perform a context-bound self-analysis, set-up a personal development plan, take actions accordingly, reflect on their actions and update their goals and plan if necessary (see *Fig. 3*). Feedback from the above-mentioned learning activities helps students to formulate their learning goals. To facilitate this process, students are introduced to techniques such as SWOT analysis, SMART goals and the core quality model. In a next step, students are asked to write a personal development plan. This way, they gather knowledge necessary for LLL and work on their skills and attitude towards lifelong learning.

Fig. 3. Cycle of learning

2.1 Context-bound self-analysis

A first part of the course is a self-analysis. In an introductory course manual, students are introduced into frameworks for self-assessment like the core qualities model of Daniel Ofman [9], a SWOT (strength-weakness-opportunities-threats) analysis etc. Then they are asked to do a self-analysis. This self-analysis should be within the given context, namely their role as a professional. It is therefore important that students have at least an idea of this context. This is provided to them throughout the curriculum, for instance in the form of company visits, project work with real-life cases etc. Extra information is provided by referring to the publications of the ‘Prefer’-project, where three different roles for engineers are defined with their accompanying competencies

[10]. A list with competencies and their common definitions is also provided to the students. Since making accurate self-assessment is known to be difficult for novices [11], students are explicitly tasked with integrating reflection on previously received feedback from teachers and peers in other courses (in particular group project work).

2.2 Personal development plan (PDP)

After the self-analysis, students are asked to define goals for themselves and to construct a personal development plan. These goals and the accompanying plan should be SMART: specific, measurable, achievable, realistic/relevant and timely.

The course is split up into three domains:

1. deepening of technological knowledge;
2. broadening of general knowledge;
3. soft skills and taking responsibility.

A student should plan and execute 34 hours of activities. Activities for at least eight hours of each domain should be chosen. Ten hours of activity are free, which means the student can choose to focus on one topic in these 10-18 (in combination with the eight hours of the domain) hours.

Students are free to define and find activities. To support this process, the teaching team offers and updates a page on the electronic learning platform where activities are announced. For the first two domains, these activities can be all kind of learning events, such as seminars, workshops, company visits or online courses (e.g. MOOCs). For the third domain, students should do some type of activity in which they act as socially engaged and responsible engineering students, e.g. acquaint secondary school students with the engineering curriculum, work on science popularization, be a member of the student council, ...

After construction of the PDP, students are invited for a first feedback session, which takes place in small groups (four to six students). The PDPs are discussed one by one and both the instructor and fellow students give feedback. The instructor encourages students to further develop competencies that students want to use as their selling point i.e. those things that they really are good at, as well as those competencies that are difficult for the student.

2.3 Learning

Once the personal development plan is set, students can start doing activities in order to achieve their goals. We consider the learning to happen in three steps: anticipation, activity and reflection. For each activity, a reflective form is to be completed. This form starts with 'anticipation': already before the activity students should think about which knowledge they expect to learn or which (soft) skills they intend to practice in this activity. A second part of the form is to be filled in after the activity (reflection).

For composition of the reflective forms, the 4Rs reflective model was used [12]. This model states that there are four levels in reflecting:

1. Reporting/responding
2. Relating
3. Reasoning
4. Reconstructing

Rather than providing direct instruction about this model, we used it to compose the questions in the reflective form in such a way that students perform those four steps by answering the questions. In particular, as one of the last questions, students are asked to describe how they would use what they have learned in a future professional situation. They should also compare their reflection after the activity with what they had anticipated.

Using their PDP and the reflective forms, students construct a portfolio. A reflective form about the students input in the group projects work is also added. At the end of the 6th semester another (formative) feedback moment is scheduled. At this point, feedback is given on the way students fill in the reflective forms and the PDP is re-evaluated and updated if necessary.

At the end of the last semester, students hand in their completed portfolio. This portfolio includes a reflection about the progress in the group project work and a last assignment, in which students make an overview of their strengths and how they are able to tackle their weaknesses. Again, formative feedback on the portfolio is given, and the portfolio is graded as 'pass' or 'fail'. An important reason to choose for a pass/fail system with formative feedback is to avoid that students would write 'desired' reflections instead of real reflection.

3 PRELIMINARY OBSERVATIONS

The new approach of the course has been running since October 2018. We can observe that the personal development plans that have been proposed by students are generally of a high quality. An example of a student PDP is shown in appendix 1. Students use the 10 'free' hours to do a variety of activities e.g. organizing a week internship, performing research to validate an idea for a start-up company, following an online course (MOOC), and being engaged in the organisation of a STEM event,...

However, it also transpired that for some students the feedback on the proposed PDP was crucial as they struggled to translate the instructions from the manual into goals of their own. Often, goals were not made sufficiently 'SMART': they were not expressed in way that is specific making it more difficult to assess afterwards if the goals are reached. Because they also handed in their self-analysis, the instructor could jump in with suggestions about goals, how to set them and encourage students by emphasizing their accomplishments and progress.

Some consideration about discussing the personal development plan in small groups needs to be made. On the one hand, this is often less time consuming for the instructor and students may learn from each other. Moreover, students might give relevant additional feedback to each other. Since students got to choose the feedback moment, they were in groups with fellow students they got along well. Fellow students jumped in when students had made wrong or too harsh conclusions about themselves. On the

other hand, some student might feel less open in their self-analysis when they know it will be discussed with their fellow students. For this reason, one student asked to discuss the PDP in private with the instructor.

A small-scale questionnaire with 17 respondents, loosely based on Kecskemety et al. [13], was done to assess the influence of the course on the targeted skills and students' attitude towards LLL. The inquiry was taken from students that started but not yet finished the course, as no student following the new approach has already finished the course. 15 out of 17 students report that throughout the curriculum, they have learned to self-asses their competencies. Also, 15 out of 17 students report that they have learned to set goals for themselves and to continuously (re)evaluate their learning pathway. Whereas they attribute the ability to self-asses and to re-evaluate the learning pathway mostly to the entire curriculum, more than halve of the students assign the ability to set development goals to this course in particular. 13 out of 17 students reported a significant increase in ability and skills to set up a PDP after following the first part of the course. Also, 12 out of 17 students claim that they now have developed the willingness to look out for and take advantage of formal, non-formal and informal occasions for self-development. This question was also posed to last year's students (who followed the old approach without PDP) and here 5 out 5 students answered positively. Therefore, it might be assumed that also with the new approach, the students' attitude towards lifelong learning will grow in the course of the second year.

4 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

LLL is a competency of such far-reaching importance in today's constantly evolving professional environments that no institution of higher education can afford to disregard it. We have decided to embrace LLL as it offers the best possible guarantee that our graduating students will thrive professionally – and continue to do so throughout their careers. One part of the approach was to set up a dedicated course on LLL, in which students acquire the necessary attitudes, skills and knowledge. Students are appealed to as actionable agents and self-directed learners, but at the same time they engage in fruitful and supportive dialogue with peers and coaches. Of course, LLL cannot be taught in a separate course only. To ensure that LLL is not relegated to a curricular silo position, we adopted Dochy's HILL model as a point of reference for the entire curriculum. The Dochy elements effectively scaffold the acquisition of LLL competencies across the curriculum.

For next year, we will provide the students with more examples that highlight good practices, such as the combination of working on language/soft skills and technical skills in an internship. Via social media (e.g. LinkedIn) and other initiatives, we want to give more students the opportunity to get in touch with alumni so that they can arrange short internships. In three years, focus groups with alumni (two years professional experience) will be organized in order to evaluate the current approach. One of the goals focus groups will be to uncover which characteristics of the course are perceived to be effective in contributing to the LLL goals. Also, an evaluation among staff will be set up to monitor acceptance and observed adequacy of the approach.

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ANNEX

Development goal	Development activity	Desired result	Timing/deadline	Facilities needed	Knowledge deepening (8)	Knowledge broadening (8)	Taking responsibility (8)	Free hours (10)
Get more insight into the work of an engineer	2 company visits on open company day	To get a first idea of different companies	Semester 5	Info on website 'open company day'	2			
	Follow an engineer for 1 dag (incl. survey)	To know what are the typical activities of an engineer in a day	Semester 6	Contact with engineer working in a company	2		4	
Improve networking skills	Follow training	To know how to start a professional conversation with people that I do not know	Semester 6	Training => MOOC is available		5		5
	Helping at info fair	Practice my network skills in a familiar context; I want to address at least three future students	Semester 6 (April 27 2019)	Subscribe myself for info fair			3	
	Attend network event	Show to myself that I can start a conversation with at least two different people in a professional context	Semester 7 (October 24 2019)	Network Event => Limburg engineering event				2
Deepen my knowledge on analytical	Read on chromatographic techniques	Understand how chromatography works	Semester 7	Textbook (library or database)	see movie			

techniques, in particular chromatographic techniques		(I will know if this succeeded if I can make the instruction movie)						
	Attend seminar or online course	To know the latest developments on GC	Semester 7	Look for relevant seminar or course (look at university websites, KVIV, ask professor N.)	2			
	Make an instruction movie on the use of GC that can be used in the lab	Well-explained instruction movie that is useful for next year students	Semester 8	Contact professor D.	2		1	3
Learn about ethics in professional context	Follow seminar	To know some examples of ethical questions that can arise in an engineering job	Semester 5 (Dec. 12, 2018)	Subscribe for seminar		2		